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Essential war material, modernist harbinger: unseasoned hardwood and its implications for the post-war Australian city

Introduction

Between 1942 and 1945, Australian architects and engineers within the Allied Works Council and the US Army Corps of Engineers undertook a vast program of building works to assist the campaign to drive Japanese forces northward through Papua-New Guinea, the Philippines and the Southwest Pacific and avoid invasion. Huge distances, lack of time and the need to wage a campaign from the air lay behind US General Douglas MacArthur's phrase that it would be an 'engineer's war'. By necessity, buildings such as airfields, hospitals, camps, warehouses, and other structures had to be light-weight, constructed quickly, and inevitably dropped in by air as easily handled pre-cut packages. With the lack of American and European softwoods in the Australasian region, an unlikely local material was pressed into war service - unseasoned or 'green' Australian hardwood. It was a material choice that would have profound implications for two reasons. Firstly, in the years of conflict, circumstances dictated the unprecedented innovation and experiment in lightweight timber structures. Secondly, in an echo of Lewis Mumford's poignant maxim that "war is the health of the machine"¹, the

systematisation and ruthless economy inherent in wartime timber buildings would influence the development and practice of a particular form of modern architecture in Australia in the late 1940s and 1950s.²

The Southwest Pacific Theatre (SWPA)

In the first four months of 1942, Japanese air, land and naval forces had swept everything before them in Southeast Asia. They had overrun not only the Philippines, but also Malaya, Burma, and the Dutch East Indies, and they had seized strategic areas in various island groups northeast of Australia. As early as January 1942 they had captured Rabaul and had begun construction of a major base there. Shortly afterwards, they occupied the northern Solomons, and in March they seized Lae and Salamaua, in the Australian-mandated territory of North East New Guinea. It was clear that the Japanese, in order to isolate Australia and cut her supply lines to the United States, would try to extend their conquests still farther south. In fact there was a strong possibility that Japan would attempt an invasion of the Australian continent.

With MacArthur's forces scuttled south from defeat in the Philippines, a new theatre of operations, the Southwest Pacific Area (SWPA) was established on 18 April 1942, with MacArthur as commander-in-chief. The plan was to drive the Japanese back through Papua-New Guinea and northward to Japan. To do so, it was clear that it would be a war won from the air. The distances were much greater than ever before experienced. The terrain, materials and climate did not conform to previously known areas of US combat, and nor could lessons learnt European and Middle Eastern Theatres be easily applied to this new theatre of war.³

Base sections were established. Located on the strategic northern coast of Australia, Darwin became the site for an advanced air base and a port of embarkation for troops and supplies going to more forward bases. Brisbane became the site for the main US base for the assembly, repair, and maintenance of all types of aircraft, and the principal supply base and port of debarkation north of Melbourne. Townsville was to be a secondary base for light aircraft. Headquarters USAFIA was to be in Melbourne, a city that was also to be the principal port for the debarkation of troops and supplies. Melbourne was also to be the major location for the design of the infrastructure and the mostly timber structures that would accompany the surge northward to eventual victory.

Essential War Material

During World War II steel was essential for armaments and munitions and was thus in short supply. In the massive building program required for the defence of Australia and the move north through

New Guinea, unseasoned or 'green' Australian hardwood, a building material that many design and construction professionals would have considered unsuitable, became an essential war material.

It was a choice determined by circumstance – all other materials were in short supply. Most major timber structures employed imported pines and firs. Local hardwoods were limited to simpler structures because, though the timber can be stronger than European or American hardwoods it tends to shrink and distort more during seasoning. This made large sections dimensionally unstable unless seasoned for several years. Seasoned Australian hardwood could not be readily supplied in long lengths because several years were needed to cure the timber to avoid distortion and splitting. Unseasoned hardwood could thus only be used in short lengths. The advantages of this timber were low production times and low costs, and the presence of Australian forests, which promised an abundance of the raw material. However it was a much stronger timber than imported softwood and nail joints could be used which enabled rapid construction using unskilled labour. The properties of this timber would therefore enable ruthless minimisation and a potential set of extremely efficient and economic structures that could be erected in a matter of hours or days.

Sverdrup and Parcel

A major problem however was that there were practically no US Army Engineer officers or enlisted men available for assignment to the Engineer Section in Australia. Fortunately, an American engineering firm, Sverdrup and Parcel had been at work in Australia since October 1941. Sverdrup and Parcel were engaged in designing and building airfields for an air ferry route from the Hawaiian Islands to the Philippines by way of Fiji, New Caledonia and Australia. In January 1942, Sverdrup and Parcel was given a fixed-fee contract to perform architectural and engineering services for the USAFIA, and the firm's employees were thus made available to the Engineers' Section. Under this arrangement, this firm was responsible for the preparations of designs, drawings and specifications, and for the major supervision of combined American and Australian army construction projects in Australia.

Setting up office in Melbourne

The Engineers Headquarters of the US Army Forces in Australia for the Southwest Pacific Area (SWPA) became a separate entity on the 4th February 1942. Four US officers and a stenographer moved from the Repatriation Building in St. Kilda Road to the top floor of Craig's Building in Elizabeth Street in central Melbourne. It was an old unused warehouse, the only merit of which was a large area of some-

what poorly lit floor space unobstructed except for a few haphazard partitions.

The Architectural Section of Engineer Headquarters commenced a week later on February 11th 1942 when Osborn McCutcheon, a director of the Melbourne architecture firm Bates Smart and McCutcheon (BSM), accepted the position of Chief Architect with the firm of Sverdrup and Parcel, then under contract as Architect-Engineer to the USAFIA. The next day, Otto Yuncken, a director of the Melbourne architecture firm Yuncken Freeman and Freeman, was appointed Assistant Chief Architect, and within a few days, a drawing office had been established and was in active production.

The architectural staff was assembled from local practising architects and architectural draftsmen in Melbourne, all of whom welcomed the opportunity to play some active part in the war effort. Architects known to have worked for the US Army included Alan Ralton (already at BSM); Douglas Gardiner and Philip Pearce (both of whom were to become postwar directors of BSM and lead the development of highrise building design in Australia) as well as Race Godfrey and Geoffrey Mewton. Under the office manager, Eric Hughes (later of Godfrey Spowers Hughes Mewton & Lobb), the senior staff were organised into groups. Each group, while being available for general work, were required to acquire a special and expert knowledge of some phase of the work such as camps, hospitals, warehouses, standards, airport buildings, barracks etc. This system proved very successful despite all odds, especially as from the Chief Architect down, all commenced with no knowledge of army requirements, standards or procedures. Because of this, an extraordinary amount of intensive study, research, and often experiment was necessary. For example, Melbourne architect Henry Pynor, who was in the Procurement Division of the US Army Corps of Engineers, developed a successful design for a portable and telescopic parachute drying flue (5 feet in diameter and 38 feet high). Another Melbourne architect JFW Ballantyne was responsible for the design and development of three types of laundry unit suitable for use under a range of field conditions (Portable, Mobile and Base). His mobile unit was mounted on a 7-ton trailer and 105 of these units were subsequently contracted for construction.

The Allied Works Council

Parallel and in concert with the efforts of the US Army Corps of Engineers were the activities of the Allied Works Council whose major role was the integration of the Australian and American war effort in construction in Australia. The Allied Works Council was formed in February 1942 as a response to the

need for an organization to control and co-ordinate the depleted Australian sources of manpower, heavy construction equipment, and supplies in the face of imminent Japanese invasion. The Allied Works Council had the responsibility of co-ordinating and supervising all civilian effort devoted to the construction of military defence projects. Its membership was made up of Australian civilian officials, the Chief Engineers of the US Army Forces in Australia (USAFIA) and the Royal Australian Air Force (RAAF), and the Engineer-in-Chief of the Australian Military Forces. The Allied Works Council when merged in November 1942 with the Works and Services Branch of the Australian Department of the Interior became the single organization responsible for all work executed by civilian agencies in support of the military construction program in Australia. With a staff of 4,600, it became the largest collaborative practice in Australian architectural history.⁴

The problem of drawings

From the outset there was a major and practical stumbling block to the Australian-American collaboration. At the beginning of operations there were only about 12 of the several hundred US Standard Theatre of Operations drawings available. Information had to be gathered from all possible sources, such as conversations with officers visiting Engineer Headquarters, discussions with senior NCOs, visits to Australian camps occupied by US troops, studies of Australian practice and so on. Eventually a more complete set of standard drawings became available but not before much useful work had already been carried out and an ethos of invention and resourcefulness engendered.

There were also problems with the American drawings themselves. They were unsuitable for use in their original form and it was necessary to adapt them to conform with the use of Australian hardwoods in place of American softwoods, which involved a complete revision of structural design. The drawings also had to be adapted to conform to Australian sizes of sheet materials such as corrugated iron and the use of alternative materials other than those envisaged on the American drawings. In this way the Australian Theatre of Operations or A-TO series of standard drawings came into being. As a result, actual projects, when required, could be prepared with the utmost speed. All that was required was a site layout plan and a schedule of buildings. It was common that two days would suffice for the preparation of necessary drawings and estimates for a 1000 bed hospital. These standard drawings and other documents were made available to Base Sections and thus also formed the basis of American construction projects in the region.

Wartime structures

The works program of the US Army Corps of Engineers and the Allied Works Council was vast. It involved complex logistical liaison; the speeding up of administrative procedures in procurement and construction; and the inventive substitution of conventional building materials for lightweight and structurally small and easily transportable members. Trussed structures in arched and gabled forms (some of the largest ever to be built in Australia), modular post and beam structures, and composite canvas/timber tent structures thus resulted from this repetitive systems approach to wartime construction. In Australia alone, construction completed amounted to 47 airfields, camps for staging 10 divisions plus camps for base troops, 2000 miles of roads, 11000 hospital beds, and 11 million square feet of covered storage. The bulk of this work was constructed by civilian labour organised through the Allied Works Council.

Most of the structures erected by the Allied Works Council involved the use of green Australian hardwoods. But it should also be noted that a suite of Australian, American and British-designed prefabricated steel, timber and canvas structures also accompanied these timber structures built in the SWPA. It was the exposure to not just an innovative use of timber but also the unique forms of these other structures that would have subsequent influence on postwar Australian architecture. The combination of lightweight timber and the idea of material substitution would have extraordinary influence but so also would the necessary leanness and expediency of the construction process and also the means of construction and limited detail.

Examples of the existing prefabricated structures included the Australian-designed Sidney Williams huts. These prefabricated metal huts were constructed extensively throughout the Australian theatre of operations, and especially so in the Northern Territory and Queensland. There was also the highly efficient Bailey Bridge designed by British inventor Donald Colman Bailey which was frequently used in achieving difficult river and gorge crossings in New Guinea and involves the basic idea of using trusses built up of panels instead of box girder sections. There was the Butler Hangar and the Luria Catenary Type Hangar, both of which were external lightweight steel truss structures with suspended canvas beneath to enclose the aircraft. There were also improvised mobile structures such as hospital trains and in another form, a 100 bed hospital with patients and personnel housed under canvas, the whole being readily moveable in motor trucks even special trucks for operating theatre, sterilising units etc. Another material that was used across not just the SWPA but across the globe was pierced steel plank (PSP) with the need to provide instant runway surface for fighter aircraft. The entire architectural language and struc-

tural techniques were drawn into a repetitive and hence productive process during wartime. As a result, virtually every structure found new form.

Timber structures in wartime

The majority of buildings constructed in the South-west Pacific Theatre were of timber. Designs for these structures emerged both from the US Army Corps of Engineers and the Allied Works Council. Greg Nolan has identified the major types as: huts; post and beam stores; trussed roof buildings; workshops; arched buildings; and hangar buildings.⁵

Huts

Developed as a simple gable roofed building with a timber frame sitting on timber stumps, the hut was developed to satisfy a range of widths from 4.9m (16') to 6.1m (20') as the war progressed. Cladding for roof and walls was typically corrugated iron or asbestos while windows either had top hung corrugated iron shutters or were glazed. In northern Australia, the huts' eaves were extended and in addition to the top hung shutters, openings were fitted with mosquito gauze. In 1943, the US Army Corps of Engineers devised a standardised light timber portal frame version of the hut (Nolan, 1999). The type of timber used varied according to region and remoteness. In some places, timber was flown in but for the most part, temporary sawmills were set up locally. The application of the hut types were to camps such as those at Rockhampton and Brisbane, each for 20,000 men, hospitals such as 250 bed hospitals at Seymour and Tocumwal, 1000 beds at Gatton in Queensland, prisoner of war camps, and ordnance and chemical warfare depots. The numbers of huts is difficult to predict. There must have been tens of thousands constructed. The Allied Works Council's US prefabrication program alone shipped parts for 17,000 prefabricated huts throughout the Pacific Islands between May 1943 and August 1944.

Post and Beam Stores

Post and beam stores were built all along the eastern coast of Australia during World War II. Used for general ordnance storage, these stores generally had columns spaced at 5m (16'8") and 6.1m (20') and ranged in width from 10 to 48 metres. Many of these stores had swiftly laid concrete slabs with the timber columns fixed to the floor with steel angle brackets. External cladding was generally corrugated iron or fibre cement sheet with no windows or a very small number of glazed rooflights.

Trussed roof buildings

Trussed roof buildings were also generally store buildings. Truss designs varied according to Australia

and American influence. Where American influence was not great, trusses generally had bolt and shear connector joints. These designs employed heavier but fewer timbers and were an improvised version of the traditional mortice and tenon truss type of pre-war Australian construction practice. By contrast, the US Army Corps of Engineers developed truss designs that employed larger numbers of lighter timber members that could be nailed together by hand and hence employ relatively unskilled labour, as well as greater quantities of unseasoned Australian hardwood.

Workshops and other major buildings

A number of very large buildings were developed either as unique or standardised building designs. Developed often from pre-war defence buildings such as a standard RAAF ordnance store design, these buildings had a variety of roof forms (sometimes large segmented roof structures) and while often constructed of unseasoned hardwoods their designs were not as experimental as other building types of the period.

Arched buildings

Where spans longer than 20 metres were required, the most common building form for stores was an arched structure. The most architecturally interesting structures were the arched warehouses and hangar buildings. This is where Sverdrup and Parcel's expertise was used, especially in the design of the igloo arch – developed by an Australian engineer, a French engineer, and the Chief Engineer, GHQ, SWPA.⁶ It was made up of small pieces of scrap-size timbers, principally 1 to 3 inches, and, with subsequent addition of a corrugated iron roof, provided a form of covered storage which 30 skilled men could erect in about 9 to 12 days. Designed initially as a frame for camouflage cover, this igloo-type construction was also subsequently used for warehouses and hangars. It illustrated the adjustment of designs to conform with local limitations of materials and manpower. Typically these were three pin arches constructed from light hand nailed boxed and trussed arches of green hardwood, though it is known that one such structure was built of imported US Oregon. Both American and Allied Works Council designers developed the igloo arched store building with standardised spans of 31.7 metres (104'), 32 metres (105'), and 51.8 metres (170'). Only until very recently with the construction of Ken Woolley's Exhibition Dome at Homebush in Sydney (1998), these arched buildings were the longest clear span timber structures existing in Australia.⁷

Hangar buildings

Aircraft and workshop hangars were either open ended igloo structures or trussed hangars whose shape

formed the outline of a parabola, and earned the name of 'hog-back' trusses. The trusses for this latter group of hangars were built with bolt and shear connector joints connecting pieces of green hardwood and a number were constructed in Werribee in Victoria.

The ethos behind the design of all of these structures was one of improvised minimalism and a ruthless engineered economy behind the use of a readily available material. There was no specific aesthetic intention rather a pragmatism and sense of success gained from necessity of the method. These buildings were not the result of the necessity of artifice but borne from the necessity of production.

Postwar Application

The implications of this architecture from war was an ethos of structural rationalism and systemised material and production delivery that engendered a unique postwar architecture culture especially in Melbourne, Australia - the wartime headquarters of the Southwest Pacific Theatre of Operations. Three areas of practice were immediate inheritors of this timber driven aesthetic: the pre-cut timber house; the development of the so-called Melbourne School, a group of buildings that exhibited daring structural expression; and the revision of postwar corporate practice and the emergence of the highrise curtain wall skyscraper.

The pre-cut timber house

Immediately after the cessation of hostilities, the prefabricated house was seen by architects and government bodies across the world as a potential solution to the pressing demand for housing. There was also the issue of what to do with wartime industries. Propositions therefore for steel houses such as the Beaufort (1946) and Myer Houses (1945) that were produced by aircraft factories enjoyed brief currency. Instead, it was the pre-cut timber house that was to have greater impact and application. Ironically however Australian hardwoods were often not used in these prefabricated schemes. In a reverse of the wartime situation, many of these timber houses were imported from England, Scandinavia and France.⁸ On other occasions the wartime expertise that had been gained through the use of repetitive timber construction was applied to the design but not to its material choice.

For example, Otto Yuncken's firm was involved in 'Operation Snail', the project initiated in 1948 by Colonel WS Kent-Hughes, then Victorian Minister of Transport, to attract one thousand urgently needed British migrants for employment by the Victorian Railways. In order to house such a large number, and to compensate for the inability of local resources to supply the housing upon which the whole idea depended, it was decided to seek houses from abroad.

Proposals were invited from firms in England, Sweden and Austria from which Simms Sons and Cooke of Nottingham were appointed as principal contractors for a pre-cut house yet to be designed. In January 1949, Melbourne architects Yuncken Freeman Bros, Griffiths and Simpson in association with Baxter Cox and Associates were appointed as designers and mass importation began under the name of the "Victorian Pre-Cut Housing Project". Other government departments took advantage of the speedy relief offered. By late 1950, over 2000 permanent timber houses were being supplied at a rate of forty per week to not only Victorian Railways projects throughout the state but also the State Electricity Commission's new townships of Newborough (Yallourn) and Mt Beauty (Kiewa), as well as the new town which the State Rivers and Water Supply Commission was building at Eildon.

The houses themselves were a blend of imported and locally produced components with the maximum proportion of labour content of the houses being applied at the English end. Australian components included the stumps, bearers and joists, gas or electric stove and canopy, and the installation of electricity and plumbing. The superstructure was pre-cut, packaged and marked in England and delivered in complete house lots. Most of the timbers were Swedish whitewood, dressed throughout and formed to the exact size and shape. All the timbers were kiln dried, and the external vertical lining boards were primed in England to minimise distortion during transit through the tropics. The low pitched gable roof was made up of light timber trusses. The roofing was Trafford tile pattern asbestos cement sheeting but later replaced by a specially designed interlocking aluminium sheeting. The result was a range of forty-four different house types of two, three and four bedroom homes.

In a curious turnabout, wartime systems were applied to postwar peacetime building but not in fact using the local material that arguably had helped win the war. Melbourne architect and critic Robin Boyd (1919-71) was to ask "Is Australia incapable of solving for herself this problem?"⁹ Across Australia, the pre-cut timber house in a range of designs was applied to new township designs for major postwar infrastructure projects involving hydro-electricity, transport and water supply. By the mid-1950s, it was a philosophy that inform the building of houses for remote mining towns and was exemplified by Ernest Milston and Don Hendry Fulton's Mary Kathleen uranium mining town houses in north Queensland (1956) where pre-cut timber and the module dictated modest but eminently workable house forms.¹⁰ Thus it was that the philosophy of the modularisation and prefabrication of the building system became

the rationale, while the Australian timbers were eschewed in favour of imported timbers.

The Melbourne school

The same fascination for the module of timber construction also swept through Australian architecture schools in the late 1940s and early 1950s. Spatial thinking moved from Le Corbusier's *plan libre* to a disciplined modulated approach to spatial division and expedient lightweight structural sections, an inheritance largely of wartime experience.

Modernism, as now reinterpreted, largely meant a frame with repetitive components. Flexibility became interchangeability as the 'modular plan' replaced the free plan and 'form follow(ed) form'.¹¹

University projects focussed on modular construction in residential design. Typical products were Douglas Alexandratos and Peter McIntyre's 1949 schemes for "A House for the Immediate Tomorrow". Both were of modular timber construction with lightweight panel materials and structural window mullions.¹² In practice, these concerns were translated into rigorous modular timber house designs for one-off clients but there also came a specific structural functional response to the design of postwar domestic and institutional buildings that came to be known as the Melbourne School and which encouraged designs of daring structural expression. In no other Australian city was the sense of lean structural experiment so widely felt.

Chief among the Melbourne designers exploring timber construction was Robin Boyd whose Finlay House, Warrandyte (1951) and Clemson House, Kew (1957-59) employed the repeated scissor trusses to provide dynamic butterfly roofs and shed rainwater to a single point. His Gillison House, Balwyn (1952) was an attempt to reduce the timber frame to its most basic structural essence, the diagonal of the timber stud frame, while his Richardson House, Toorak (1954) was a translation into steel of the arched forms of the workshops and hangars of wartime but with a disciplined timber box suspended between. Peter and Dione McIntyre explored lightweight timber construction with a series of eight arched roof houses. The concept of the houses was based on the idea of a flexible plan roofed by 8.2m (27') wide gently arched timber trusses supported on timber posts with the internal walls designed as panels of a standard size and which could be taken away without affecting the structure. The owners were then not only able to change the size of the rooms but also the arrangement of bedroom and living areas.

Larger structures like Kevin Borland, Peter McIntyre and John and Phyllis Murphy's Olympic Swimming Stadium, Melbourne (1953-56), while deriving much

of its formal principle from an earlier Harry Seidler competition entry (1952) for another stadium¹³, could also be read as a virtual hangar for swimming in with its marching line of canted girder trusses. Even the steel arched Basketball Stadium (1956) built in the grounds of Melbourne's Exhibition Buildings seemed to recall the arched hangars and workshops of nearby Werribee and far off Queensland. Another wartime analogy could be made with Yuncken Freeman Bros. Griffiths and Simpson's Sidney Myer Music Bowl, Melbourne (1956-59) which might be read at one level as a giant piece of camouflage netting drawn across a sunken gun emplacement rather than its final function, an innocent acoustic bowl for free concerts in a park.

While it is clear that unseasoned Australian hardwood plays little direct part in any of these postwar structures, there is little doubt that the wartime construction experience had affected the design methods of Melbourne architects and contributed to a very specific line of architectural enquiry in that city. It should also be noted that no causal link is being claimed here rather the fact noted that in previous histories of postwar Australian architecture, the impact of war has been overlooked and not seen as a potential design source (one amongst many) for Melbourne's original contributions to a postwar Australian architecture.

Postwar practice and the highrise building

Perhaps most significantly and surprisingly, the implications of wartime uses of timber can be seen in the most urbanistically influential of postwar structures: the glazed curtain wall skyscraper. Through a complete revision of production technology, material and labour mobilisation, and an associated aesthetic that was transferred from the wartime use of timber to the repetitive glass and steel facades of the postwar city, architects began to turn wartime experience to the task of building for the new postwar commercial world.

In Melbourne (and largely Australia), the advanced design of the postwar skyscraper was pioneered by Osborn McCutcheon and his staff. On Australia's entry in 1942 into World War II, McCutcheon held the position of Chief Architect of the Corps of Engineers of the US Army in the South West Pacific Area from 1942-1944. Joining him in the Corps of Engineers was another BSM partner since 1937, Alan Ralton. War was a time of revelation for McCutcheon as the development of repetitive building systems and programs of mobilisation were crucial to the efficiency of the wartime enterprise. Systematisation, standardisation and the speed of industrial production formed the core relationship between architects

and wartime industry. Methods and processes of prefabrication, dry systems of construction, and the co-ordination of teams of specialists combined with efficient systems of delivery were paramount. War was a time when the modernist dream of the machine was realised, when the construction industry was forced to match the pressures of military mobilisation at a scale not experienced by any previous conflict. Indeed the mechanisation of World War II was the impetus for an entirely new aesthetic of postwar architecture that US firms like Skidmore Owings and Merrill, architects of numerous wartime projects, would take up with alacrity. It was a modernist aesthetic not of cubist abstraction but one of system building, repetition and modular planning, and of which the glass curtain wall modulated by aluminium framing (a material refined in application by its use during World War II) was found to be the thinnest, lightest and most efficiently erected skin. At the conclusion of hostilities, McCutcheon invited two other on-time members of the Corps of Engineers to join him in BSM's postwar practice. Douglas B Gardiner and Phillip F Pearce joined BSM as partners in 1945. Both had between 1942 and 1944 worked closely with McCutcheon in wartime operations and Pearce had extended this experience as Senior Planning Officer in the War Homes Division of the Commonwealth Government 1944-1945. McCutcheon similarly had enriched his wartime experience as Controller of Planning and Chief Technical Adviser on Housing to the Commonwealth Government, 1944-46.

From 1945, BSM transformed their practice techniques and procedures. The design aesthetic of the office was also transformed. After returning to private practice, McCutcheon travelled overseas to the United States, England and Europe. On his return, the firm commenced an intensive study of lightweight construction methods. Some of these principles were applied to new housing at BSM's Eildon Township (1950-56) and also to high-rise building design most notably the six MLC Building projects in Brisbane (1955), Perth (1956), Wollongong (1956), Adelaide (1957), Newcastle (1957) and Sydney (1957). McCutcheon introduced the notion of teams of specialists within a multi-disciplinary office. He was an advocate of integrated thinking and integrated systems. There were seven departments: architects; structural engineers; services; estimating; interior design; accounting; and general clerical and filing. He had, in effect, recast his Melbourne office as the US Army Corps of Engineers.

The exemplar of McCutcheon and his collaborator's search for the system built skyscraper was ICI House, Melbourne (1955-58) – a building essentially of dry construction and prefabricated parts that had emerged from an office which had been

entirely restructured after World War II as teams of specialists by its principal director.¹⁴ It was as if the high rise building was a wartime structure. Repetition, the module, the kit of parts with glass and lightweight infill panels, and documented, assembled, and delivered in tendered packages – the analogy is altogether too neat but also compelling in that the similarities are startling. Once again, while there is clearly no unseasoned Australian hardwood being used in the design of the postwar glazed skyscraper, the question of influence is hard to ignore. Previous histories of the postwar skyscraper constantly hark back to the birth of the skyscraper in 19th century Chicago or the visionary glass tower schemes (1921) by Ludwig Mies van der Rohe or the Van der Nelle Factory, Rotterdam (1926-30). They dwell little on the influence of World War II and its associated and circumstantial aesthetic of engineered scientism. Even histories of the work of Skidmore Owings and Merrill, the American skyscraper firm par excellence make no reference to the effect of war nor give reasons for the appearance of a building such as Lever House.

Modernist Harbinger

Architectural histories often indicate that times of war are times of minimal architectural production. Yet one needs to ask: where do architects go during wartime and are their architectural services rendered obsolete? The effects and implications of war on the practice of architecture is a relatively little studied and little understood subject. Renaissance architecture included expertise in military architecture as a necessary and founding component of architectural practice. But twentieth century architectural histories have tended to overlook that pedigree and instead use the dates of war as benchmarks for changes in style rather than examining the direct effect and implications of war upon architectural practice; building technologies; project construction and delivery; and on an aesthetic that is associated with the mechanics of war. The prevailing canon of 20th century architectural history has been to follow the international trend of examining architectural movements through the medium of the house, rather than through public, industrial or commercial architecture, and inevitably through the framework of progressive modernism rather than through frameworks of social and political change. In particular, the effects of wartime, when issues of building production and delivery take primary position over aesthetics, fashion and style – these have not been considered. By examining such a modest material as unseasoned Australian hardwood, one can begin to speculate that far from being irrelevant, it was not only an essential war material, but it also was an important if unlikely Modernist harbinger.

Fig. 1 – Erection of prefabricated framework. Three hundred feet of roof trusses were erected in six days by 12 men. Meeandah – Warehouse construction. July 1943. Item 53.3/3.4, box 18, series B5281, National Archives of Australia.

Fig. 2 – Carpenters pre-fabricating bow-truss cord [sic] on specially constructed table. Rydlemere. Construction US Stores. February 1943. Item 53.1/2.4, box 17, series B5281, National Archives of Australia.

Fig. 3 – View of walls, abutment pads and arches. 2nd store in similar stage of construction. Rydlemere. Construction US Stores. February 1943. Item 53.1/2.7, box 17, series B5281, National Archives of Australia.

Fig. 4 – A B-17 is parked inside a repair hangar at an Engineer installation at 4th Air Depot, Townsville, Australia December 1942. Photograph: Pvt Joseph Herda. Signal Corps Photo #GHQ-SWPA-SC-43-169-19S-147E/sc 166048. Held National Archives and Records Administration, College Park, Maryland, USA.

Fig. 5 – Construction of bows of repair hangar 46 hangar at an Engineer installation at 4th Air Depot, Townsville, Australia December 1942. Photograph: Pvt Joseph Herda. Signal Corps Photo #GHQ-SWPA-SC-43-2418-19S-147E/SC166054. Held National Archives and Records Administration, College Park, Maryland, USA.

Fig. 6 – Yuncken, Freeman Bros., Griffiths and Simpson, Sidney Myer Music Bowl, Melbourne (1956-59).
Photographer unknown, c.1959. Held collection of Philip Good.

Fig. 9 – Kevin Borland, Peter McIntyre and John and Phyllis Murphy, Olympic Swimming Stadium, Melbourne, (1953-56).
Photograph © Wolfgang Sievers. Reproduced with permission.

Fig. 7 – Members of the [Civil Construction Corps] mobile unit wheeling prefabricated bow trusses into position for erection. Townsville – Garbutt – RAAF Store. July 1943.
Item 53.3/1.4, box 18, series B5281, National Archives of Australia.

Fig. 10 – Robin Boyd, Richardson House, Toorak, VIC, 1954.
Photograph © Wolfgang Sievers. Reproduced with permission.

Fig. 8 – Bates, Smart and McCutcheon, ICI House, Melbourne (1955-58).
Photograph © Wolfgang Sievers. Reproduced with permission.

Fig. 11 – Adelaide River (AWAS Camp), c.1943. Item 52.2/1.1, box 16, series B5281, National Archives of Australia.

NOTES

¹ Donald Albrecht (ed.), *World War II and the American Dream: How Wartime Building Changed a Nation*, Cambridge, Mass.: National Building Museum and MIT Press, 1995, p. xvi.

² Research for this paper was undertaken in June/July 1999 by the authors as part of an Australian Research Council Small Grant. Most of the historical data, archival material, and pictorial images were sourced from files held at the National Archives and Records Administration in College Park, Maryland, the library of the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers at Fort Belvoir, Virginia, and the Library of Congress, Washington DC.

³ Office of the Chief Engineer, General Headquarters Army Forces, *Engineers of the Southwest Pacific 1941-45, Volume I (Engineers in Theatre Operations)*, Reports of Operations, United States Army Forces in the Far East Southwest Pacific Area, 1947.

⁴ Allied Works Council, *Report on the activities of the Allied Works Council for the period July 1 1943 - February 15 1945*, Sydney, 1945.

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Architecture, Australia, war, timber, Modernism

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